

Supplementary material for the Koli Ontology

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Koli Ontology

Table 1: **Site Classes:** Concepts related to the heritage site

Name	Description	Superclass
Touristic Site	A natural or cultural location open to the public for recreational, educational, or aesthetic purposes	E27 Site
Cultural Heritage Site	A place of significance recognised for its enduring cultural, symbolic, or historical value	E27 Site
Spiritual Ritual Site	A natural or designated location historically or symbolically associated with ritualistic, spiritual, or religious practices	E27 Site
Natural Heritage Site	A location of outstanding geological, ecological, or scenic value, often protected for its environmental significance	E27 Site
Park	A designated area preserved for its natural environment and public enjoyment	Natural Heritage Site
Hill	A naturally raised area of land, smaller than a mountain	Natural Heritage Site
Lake	A large body of water surrounded by land	Natural Heritage Site
Fissure	A narrow opening or crack typically resulting from geological processes	Natural Heritage Site

Cave	A natural underground space typically formed by the weathering of rock	Natural Heritage Site
Cultural Landscape Site	A landscape that has been shaped or symbolically interpreted through cultural practices, beliefs, or artistic representation	E27 Site

Table 2: **Actor Classes:** Concepts related to actors associated with the site

Name	Description	Superclass
Institution	An organised body responsible for research, preservation, or management of cultural/natural heritage	E74 Group
Artist	An individual whose creative work reflects or engages with the heritage site	E21 Person

Table 3: **Geographical features classes:** Concepts related to the environmental surroundings

Name	Description	Superclass
Climate	A feature regarding weather conditions	E26 Physical Feature
Landscape	Landscape includes physical and natural elements, as well as human elements such as built structures	E26 Physical Feature
Cultural Landscape	A landscape containing features made by humans. It can be protected as a cultural heritage site	Landscape
Rural Landscape	A field characterized by green areas with diverse vegetation	Cultural Landscape
Urban Landscape	This type of landscape refers to a space like a city that contains physical and visual elements built by humans	Cultural Landscape
Soundscape	Set of sounds typical from an environment	E26 Physical Feature

Table 3 Continued from previous page (Geographical features)

Name	Description	Superclass
Natural Sound-scape	Sounds of nature in its characteristic environment	Soundscape
Bird sounds	The sounds of birds chirping	Natural soundscape
Tree Branches sounds	The sounds of tree Branches moving	Natural soundscape
Wind blowing sounds	The sounds of the wind blowing	Natural soundscape
Region	A geographical unit that can aggregate multiple districts	E53 Place
District	A subdivision of a region that can encompass multiple municipalities within boundaries	E53 Place
Municipality	The second-level administrative division after the district, with its own jurisdiction and local government	E53 Place
Parish	A minor administrative division, sub part of Municipalities	E53 Place
Coordinates	A specific location in space	E94 Space Primitive

Table 4: **Event -classes**: Concepts related to events and time associated with the monument

Name	Description	Superclass
Paleoproterozoic	A geological period dating from approximately 2.5 to 1.6 billion years ago	E4 Period
Neolithic	A specific period from pre-history marked by early farming and stone tools	E4 Period
Late Neolithic	The later phase of the Neolithic period, associated with complex societies and megalithic monuments	Neolithic
Formation	The geological or natural formation of the site or landscape	E7 Activity

Table 4 Continued from previous page (Event Classes)

Name	Description	Superclass
Occupation/Usage	The human usage or inhabitation of a site over a period of time	E7 Activity
Romanticism	An artistic and intellectual movement emphasizing nature, emotion, and individualism, often associated with the 19th century	E7 Activity

Table 5: Site/Instances

Name	Description	Class
Koli	Hill area in North Karelia, Finland, with geological, cultural and symbolic importance	- Natural Heritage Site - Cultural Heritage Site - Cultural Landscape Site - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Ukko-Koli Hill	The highest summit in the Koli hill chain, known for panoramic views	- Natural Heritage Site - Hill - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Akka-Koli Hill	One of the main hilltops of the Koli area, part of the iconic triad	- Natural Heritage Site - Hill - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Paha-Koli Hill	One of the main hilltops of the Koli area, part of the iconic triad	- Natural Heritage Site - Hill - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Mäkrävaara Hill	One of the main hilltops of the Koli area.	- Natural Heritage Site - Hill - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site

Table 5 Continued from previous page (Site Instances)

Name	Description	Class
Paimenenvaara Hill	One of the main hilltops of the Koli area.	- Natural Heritage Site - Hill - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Pieni-Koli Hill	A small hill of the Koli area.	- Natural Heritage Site - Hill - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Pirunkirkko	Cave-like fissure associated with ritual or spiritual use	- Natural Heritage Site - Cave - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Uhrihalkeama	A sacrificial crack or fissure in the rock, interpreted as a ritual site	- Natural Heritage Site - Fissure - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site
Lake Pielinen	Large lake viewed from Koli's peaks, integral to the landscape	- Natural Heritage Site - Lake - Spiritual Ritual Site - Touristic Site

Table 6: Actor/Instances Koli - Table 6

Name	Description	Class
Metsähallitus	Institution responsible for environmental and landscape research in the Koli area	Institution
Koli Cultural Society	Founded in 1999. The purpose of the Society is to maintain and to enliven the cultural life in Koli. The Society organizes cultural events in the Koli area.	Institution

Table 6 Continued from previous page (Instances of Actors)

Name	Description	Class
Koli Nature Centre Ukko	The purpose of the Nature Centre Ukko is to promote, preserve, and enliven the natural and cultural heritage of Koli, offering visitors meaningful experiences through guided excursions, exhibitions, and educational services.	Institution
Eero Järnefelt	Finnish painter known for landscapes of Koli	Artist
Ilmari Aalto	Finnish artist influenced by Koli's natural scenery	Artist
Juhani Aho	Finnish writer who described and promoted Koli's symbolism	Artist
Jean Sibelius	Composer inspired by Finnish landscapes including Koli	Artist
Alfred William Finch	Painter associated with Symbolism and Nordic natural landscapes	Artist
Pekka Halonen	Finnish painter known for depicting Finnish winter landscapes and rural life	Artist
Venny Soldan-Brofeldt	Finnish painter and illustrator associated with the National Romantic movement	Artist
I.K. Inha	Finnish photographer and writer who documented the Karelian landscape and cultural heritage	Artist

Table 7: Geographic feature/Instances Koli - Table 3

Name	Description	Class
North Karelia	A region in Eastern Finland where Koli is located	Region
Lieksa	A municipality in the region of North Karelia	Municipality
63.094444, _29.808611	GPS coordinates of Koli	Coordinates

Table 7 Continued from previous page (Geographic Instances)

Name	Description	Class
Humid Continental Climate	Climate characterized by seasonal temperature variation and significant precipitation	Climate
Boreal Forest Upland Landscape	A landscape dominated by taiga and mixed coniferous forest characteristic of the Koli region	Landscape

Table 8: **Event/Instances** Koli - Table 2

Name	Description	Class
300000000 - 2000000000	Time span covering formation processes of early Precambrian geology	E52 Time Span
19th Century – 21st Century	Time associated with the Romantic movement and artistic engagement with Koli	E52 Time Span
1991-1994	Years in which Koli was recognised as a national landscape	E52 Time Span
Formation of Koli	Natural geological formation process of the Koli hill chain	Formation
Occupation or Usage of Koli	Human interaction and potential ritual usage of the Koli landscape	Occupation/Usage
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	The symbolic, artistic and emotional association of Romantic artists with the site	Romanticism

Table 9: **Data Properties** Koli

Instance	Property	Value
Koli	rockType	(str) gneissGranite
Koli	rockType	(str) gneissGranodiorite
Koli	rockType	(str) gneissTrondhjemite

Table 10: **Object Properties Koli**

Instance	Relation (Property)	Instance
Koli	P53 has former or current location	Lieksa
Lieksa	P89 falls within	North Karelia
North Karelia	hasTypicalLandscape	Boreal Forest Upland
North Karelia	hasClimate	Humid Continental Climate
Formation of Koli	hasFormationTimeSpan	3B - 2B
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	hasArtisticTimeSpan	19thCentury – 21st Century
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	P8 took place on or within	Koli
Occupation or Usage of Koli	P8 took place on or within	Koli
Identification of Koli	P8 took place on or within	Koli
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	P14 carried Out By	Eero Järnefelt
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	P14 carried Out By	Ilmari Aalto
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	P14 carried Out By	Juhani Aho
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	P14 carried Out By	Jean Sibelius
Romanticist Engagement with Koli	P14 carried Out By	Alfred William Finch
NrtKoli1	P129 is about	Ukko-Koli Hill
ImgKoli1	P129 is about	Ukko-Koli Hill
NrtKoli2	P129 is about	Lake Pielinen
ImgKoli2	P129 is about	Lake Pielinen

Demonstrator

Table 11: **Demonstrator Classes**: Phygital elements associated the heritage site

Name	Description	Superclass
E71 Human-Made Thing	Discrete, identifiable items created by humans, either physical or intellectual, with relative stability	E1 CRM Entity
Demonstrator	A prototype or tool created to showcase a concept or functionality	E71 Human-Made Thing
App	A software application designed to guide or assist users, often in cultural or educational contexts	E31 Document
Audio	Audio files	E31 Document
Image	Image files	E31 Document
Video	Video files	E31 Document
Text	The written files of the interviews	E31 Document

Table 12: **Demonstrator/Instances Site** – Table 11

Name	Description	Class
AudSite1–AudSiteX	Audio files related to Site	Audio
ImgSite1–ImgSiteX	Image files related to Site	Image
VidSite1–VidSiteX	Video files related to Site	Video
NrtSite1–NrtSiteX	Collected narratives related to Site	Narrative

Table 13: **Data Properties**

Instance	Property	Value
E31 Document	link	(anyURI) https://....

Table 14: **Object Properties**

Domain	Relation (Property)	Range
E18 Physical Thing	P46 is ComposedOf	E18 Physical Thing

Table 14 Continued from previous page (Object Properties)

Domain	Relation (Property)	Range
E89 Propositional Object	P129 is about	E1 CRM Entity

Table 15: Data Properties Site/Instance

Instance	Property	Value
AudSite1	link	(anyURI) https://....
ImgSite1	link	(anyURI) https://....
VidSite1	link	(anyURI) https://....

Table 16: Object Properties Site/Instance

Instance	Relation (Property)	Instance
ImgSite1	P129 is about	Site
TextSite1	P129 is about	Site
VidSite1	P129 is about	Site

Adding semantics to media objects

In the next page, a graph illustrates the kind of knowledge that may be associated to one video representing Koli, according to the proposed structure.

